

DAMAGE PREDICTION DUE TO SIMULTANEOUS MULTIPLE IMPACTS IN COMPOSITES USING PERIDYNAMICS

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ABSTRACT

This study demonstrates the application of peridynamics to predict complex failure modes and damage progression in composite laminates subjected to simultaneous impacts. A transient analysis is performed for simulating the motion of rigid impactors based on the concepts from multi-body dynamics and appropriate contact law between the impactor and target (laminate). Deformation and damage in the target is calculated by performing transient peridynamic analysis without special procedures, making progressive failure analysis more practical. The peridynamic simulations capture the damage patterns effectively due to simultaneous impacts.

1 INTRODUCTION

Advanced composites are increasingly used in components for defense applications as well as commercial structures (e.g., the Boeing 787 and Airbus 380). During a component's service life, damage due to high or low energy impact may be introduced, which may lead to premature failure of these structures. Experimental evaluation of damage that is not visible involves expensive specialized equipment, and may not be fully satisfactory in visualization of internal damage. Component level structural testing and analysis of advanced composites is prohibitively expensive and time consuming. Instead, using robust and accurate computational tools complemented by experiments at key stages is a viable and cost-effective option.

However, there is no analysis capability that can predict all possible failure modes concerning advanced composites because damage initiation and its progressive growth are very complex. Commonly accepted methods, such as finite element method or smoothed-particle hydrodynamics, require special treatments. Existing computational methods for modeling fracture in a continuous body are based on the partial differential equations (PDEs) of classical continuum mechanics. These methods suffer from the inherent limitation that the spatial derivatives required by the PDEs do not, by definition, exist at crack tips or along crack surfaces. Therefore, the basic mathematical structure of the formulation breaks down whenever a crack appears in a body. Various special techniques have been developed in fracture mechanics to deal with this limitation. Generally, these techniques involve redefining a body in such a way as to exclude the crack, then applying conditions at the crack surfaces as boundary conditions.

An alternative to traditional FEA is the peridynamic (PD) theory introduced by Silling [1, 2]; it is a nonlocal extension of classical continuum mechanics. The PD theory is based on integro-differential equations involving time and spatial coordinates. The PD equation of motion differs from that of classical theory continuum mechanics, which is based on partial differential equations. The PD analysis provides the nonlinear material response with respect to displacements. Furthermore, the material response includes damage in the PD theory. This feature allows damage initiation and propagation at multiple sites with arbitrary paths inside the material without resorting to special crack growth criteria. In the PD theory, internal forces are expressed through nonlocal interactions between pairs of material points within a continuous body, and damage is a part of the constitutive model. Damage prediction in PD theory is more realistic than the methods utilizing the classical continuum

theory since the PD theory considers material failure as a part of the material response without resorting to any external damage criterion. Therefore, the PD theory appears to be the best candidate for damage assessment in advanced composite structures.

The bond-based PD theory was successfully used to predict damage in laminated composites subjected to low velocity impact and damage in woven composites subjected to static indentation by Askari et al. [3] and Colavito et. al. [4, 5]. Failure in notched composites under bi-axial loading was considered by Xu et. al.[6]. Kilic et. al. [7], Oterkus and Madenci [8], and Hu et. al.[9] predicted failure modes of fiber, matrix and delamination in various center-cracked laminates under tension. Recently, Oterkus and Madenci [10] demonstrated the capability of the “ordinary state-based” peridynamics to capture the failure modes in center-cracked laminates under tension. The ability of PD to predict the failure initiation and modes in composites has been demonstrated in these previous studies.

This study demonstrates the application of peridynamics to predict complex failure modes and damage paths in laminated composites subjected to simultaneous multiple impacts. A transient analysis is performed for simulating the motion of rigid impactors based on the concepts from multi-body dynamics with appropriate contact law between the impactor and target. It successfully predicts complex damage patterns in laminated composite structures subjected to simultaneous multiple impactors.

2 PERIDYNAMIC LAMINATE THEORY

In the PD theory, material points interact with each other directly through the prescribed response function, which contains all of the constitutive information associated with the material. The response function includes a length parameter called internal length (horizon), δ . The locality of interactions depends on the horizon, and interactions become more local with a decreasing horizon. Hence, the classical theory of elasticity can be considered as a limiting case of the PD theory as the internal length approaches zero. As the interactions between material points cease, cracks may initiate and align themselves along surfaces that form cracks, yet the integral equations continue to remain valid.

Fig. 1. Elevation of each lamina in a laminate and PD material points

Each fiber-reinforced composite lamina of a laminate shown in Fig. 1 is idealized as a two-dimensional structure with the directional dependency of the interactions between the peridynamic material points. As shown in Fig. 2, the material point (q) represents material points that interact with material point (k) only along the fiber direction with an orientation angle of θ in reference to the x -axis. Similarly, material point (r) represents material points that interact with material point (k) only along the transverse direction. However, the material point (p) represents material points that interact with material point (k) in any direction, including the fiber and transverse directions. The orientation of a PD interaction between the material point (k) and the material point (p) is defined by the angle ϕ with respect to the x -axis. The domain of integration, H shown in Fig. 2, is a disk with radius δ and thickness, h . The material points in a particular lamina interact with the other material points of immediate neighboring laminae; above and below it.

Fig. 2. PD horizon for a family of material points and their interactions in a lamina.

As shown in Fig. 1, the reference coordinate system (x, y, z) is located on the mid-plane of the laminate. The laminate thickness, h is given by

$$h = \sum_{n=1}^N h_n \quad (1)$$

where N is the total number of lamina in the stacking sequence, and h_n is the thickness of n^{th} lamina. With respect to the mid-plane, the position of each lamina, z_n is defined as

$$z_n = -\frac{h}{2} + \sum_{m=1}^{n-1} h_m + \frac{1}{2} h_n \quad (2)$$

As derived by Madenci and Oterkus [11], the equation of motion for material point $\mathbf{x}_{(k)}^n$ located on the n^{th} layer of a laminate with N layers can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{(k)}^n \ddot{\mathbf{u}}_{(k)}^n = & \sum_{j=1}^n \left[\mathbf{t}_{(k)(j)}^n (\mathbf{u}_{(j)}^n - \mathbf{u}_{(k)}^n, \mathbf{x}_{(j)}^n - \mathbf{x}_{(k)}^n, t) - \mathbf{t}_{(j)(k)}^n (\mathbf{u}_{(k)}^n - \mathbf{u}_{(j)}^n, \mathbf{x}_{(k)}^n - \mathbf{x}_{(j)}^n, t) \right] V_{(j)}^n \\ & + \sum_{m=n+1, n-1} \mathbf{p}_{(k)}^{(n)(m)} V_{(k)}^m + 2 \sum_{m=n+1, n-1} \sum_{j=1}^m \mathbf{q}_{(k)(j)}^{(n)(m)} V_{(j)}^m + \mathbf{b}_{(k)}^n \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where the material point, $\mathbf{x}_{(k)}^n$ on the n^{th} layer is associated with an incremental volume, $V_{(k)}^n$ and a mass density of $\rho_{(k)}^n$; t designates time. With respect to a Cartesian coordinate system, the material point $\mathbf{x}_{(k)}^n$ experiences displacement, $\mathbf{u}_{(k)}^n$, and its location is described by the position vector, $\mathbf{y}_{(k)}$ in the deformed state. The displacement and body load vectors at material point, $\mathbf{x}_{(k)}^n$, are represented by $\mathbf{u}_{(k)}^n$ and $\mathbf{b}_{(k)}^n$, respectively. The motion of a material point conforms to the Lagrangian description of motion.

Arising from in-plane deformation, $\mathbf{t}_{(k)(j)}^n$ represents the force density that material point, $\mathbf{x}_{(j)}^n$ exerts upon material point, $\mathbf{x}_{(k)}^n$. The force density vectors, $\mathbf{p}_{(k)}^{(n)(m)}$ and $\mathbf{q}_{(k)(j)}^{(n)(m)}$ with $m = (n+1), (n-1)$ develop due to the transverse normal and transverse shear deformations, respectively, between the material points $\mathbf{x}_{(k)}^n$ and $\mathbf{x}_{(k)}^m$. The explicit form of the force density vectors, $\mathbf{t}_{(k)(j)}^n$, $\mathbf{p}_{(k)}^{(n)(m)}$ and $\mathbf{q}_{(k)(j)}^{(n)(m)}$ associated

with in-plane and transverse deformations, respectively, are explicitly derived by Madenci and Oterkus [11] in the form

$$\mathbf{t}_{(k)(j)}^{(n)} = 2\delta \left(ad \frac{\Lambda_{(k)(j)}^n}{|\mathbf{x}_{(j)}^n - \mathbf{x}_{(k)}^n|} \theta_{(k)}^n + (\mu_F b_F + b_{FT} + \mu_T b_T) s_{(k)(j)}^{(n)} \right) \frac{\mathbf{y}_{(j)}^n - \mathbf{y}_{(k)}^n}{|\mathbf{y}_{(j)}^n - \mathbf{y}_{(k)}^n|} \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{p}_{(k)}^{(n)(m)} = 4b_N \left(|\mathbf{y}_{(k)}^m - \mathbf{y}_{(k)}^n| - |\mathbf{x}_{(k)}^m - \mathbf{x}_{(k)}^n| \right) \frac{\mathbf{y}_{(k)}^m - \mathbf{y}_{(k)}^n}{|\mathbf{y}_{(k)}^m - \mathbf{y}_{(k)}^n|} \quad (5)$$

and

$$\mathbf{q}_{(k)(j)}^{(n)(m)} = 4b_S \left[\frac{|\mathbf{y}_{(j)}^m - \mathbf{y}_{(k)}^n| - |\mathbf{x}_{(j)}^m - \mathbf{x}_{(k)}^n|}{|\mathbf{x}_{(j)}^m - \mathbf{x}_{(k)}^n|} - \frac{|\mathbf{y}_{(k)}^m - \mathbf{y}_{(j)}^n| - |\mathbf{x}_{(k)}^m - \mathbf{x}_{(j)}^n|}{|\mathbf{x}_{(k)}^m - \mathbf{x}_{(j)}^n|} \right] \frac{\mathbf{y}_{(j)}^m - \mathbf{y}_{(k)}^n}{|\mathbf{y}_{(j)}^m - \mathbf{y}_{(k)}^n|} \quad (6)$$

with

$$s_{(k)(j)}^{(n)} = \frac{|\mathbf{y}_{(j)}^n - \mathbf{y}_{(k)}^n| - |\mathbf{x}_{(j)}^n - \mathbf{x}_{(k)}^n|}{|\mathbf{x}_{(j)}^n - \mathbf{x}_{(k)}^n|} \quad (7)$$

and

$$\mu_F = \begin{cases} 1 & (\mathbf{x}_{(j)} - \mathbf{x}_{(k)}) // \text{fiber direction} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

and

$$\mu_T = \begin{cases} 1 & (\mathbf{x}_{(j)} - \mathbf{x}_{(k)}) \perp \text{fiber direction} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

The parameter $\theta_{(k)}$ is defined as

$$\theta_{(k)}^n = d \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{\delta}{|\mathbf{x}_{(j)}^n - \mathbf{x}_{(k)}^n|} \left(|\mathbf{y}_{(j)}^n - \mathbf{y}_{(k)}^n| - |\mathbf{x}_{(j)}^n - \mathbf{x}_{(k)}^n| \right) \Lambda_{(k)(j)}^n V_{(j)}^n, \quad (10)$$

The direction cosines of the relative position vectors between the material points $\mathbf{x}_{(k)}^n$ and $\mathbf{x}_{(j)}^n$ in the undeformed and deformed states are defined as

$$\Lambda_{(k)(j)}^n = \frac{(\mathbf{y}_{(j)} - \mathbf{y}_{(k)}) \cdot (\mathbf{x}_{(j)} - \mathbf{x}_{(k)})}{|\mathbf{y}_{(j)} - \mathbf{y}_{(k)}| |\mathbf{x}_{(j)} - \mathbf{x}_{(k)}|} \quad (11)$$

The PD material parameters, b_F , b_T and b_{FT} are associated with deformation of material points in the fiber direction, transverse direction, and remaining arbitrary directions, respectively. The PD material parameters b_N and b_S are associated with the transverse normal and shear deformations. As derived by Madenci and Oterkus [11], the parameters can be related to the four independent material constants of elastic modulus in the fiber direction, E_{11} , elastic modulus in the transverse direction, E_{22} , in-plane shear modulus, G_{12} , and in-plane Poisson's ratio, ν_{12} . The resulting peridynamic model of a laminate

consists of laminae connected with transverse normal and shear deformations, and it accurately models the behavior of fiber reinforced laminate composites.

Local damage at a point is defined as the weighted ratio of the number of eliminated interactions to the total number of initial interactions of a material point with its family members. The local damage at a point can be quantified as (Silling and Askari, [12])

$$\varphi(\mathbf{x}, t) = 1 - \frac{\int_H \mu(\mathbf{x}' - \mathbf{x}, t) dV'}{\int_H dV'} \quad (12)$$

The local damage ranges from zero to one. When the local damage is one all the interactions initially associated with the point have been eliminated, while a local damage of zero means that all interactions are intact. The measure of local damage is an indicator of possible crack formation within a body. For example, initially a material point interacts with all materials in its horizon as shown in Fig. 3 (a); thus, the local damage has a value of 0. However, the creation of a crack terminates half of the interactions within its horizon resulting in a local damage value of 1/2 as depicted in Fig. 3 (b).

Fig. 3. a) All interactions are intact, b) Half of the interactions are terminated

The constitutive or force-stretch relations for the interactions within the plane of a lamina, in the fiber, transverse, and arbitrary directions, are shown in Fig. 4. In this study, the transverse and arbitrary critical parameters are combined into a matrix critical stretch in tension and compression as s_{mt} and s_{mc} , respectively. The critical parameter in the fiber direction in tension and compression are s_{ft} and s_{fc} , respectively. The critical stretch parameters for composite laminates can be obtained by using experimental methods [13], calibration through an inverse approach, or through equating the energy required to create a fracture surface to the energy release rate.

Fig. 4. Force-stretch relationships for peridynamic interactions

3 NUMERICAL RESULTS

The numerical results concern a laminate subjected to two simultaneous impactors. The impactors are rigid and cylindrical in shape with flat ends. As shown in Fig. 5, one of the impactors hits the center of top surface at point A with $(x=0, y=0, z=H_L)$ while the other impactor hits at point B with $(x=0.009 \text{ m}, y=0.009 \text{ m}, z=H_L)$ close to the center. A Cartesian coordinate system is located at

the center of bottom surface of the laminate. The laminate is square with an edge dimension of $L=W=0.179$ m and with a thickness of $H_L=0.013$ m. The laminate is made of 8 woven orthotropic layers with elastic material properties specified as $E_1 = E_2 = 127.5$ GPa, $E_3 = 11.8$ GPa, $\nu_{21} = \nu_{31} = .11$, $\nu_{32} = .18$, $G_{12} = 2.9$ GPa, $G_{13} = G_{23} = 2.14$ GPa, and its mass density as $\rho = 1850$ kg/m³. The thickness of each layer is specified as $t_k = H_L / 8$. The critical stretch of matrix, transverse peel and shear are set to 0.01, 0.08 and 0.08, respectively.

In order to simulate the common test conditions, the bottom and top surfaces of the laminate are restrained in the z -direction except for the circular region as shown in Fig. 5. The diameter of the circular region is specified as $D_f = 0.1$ m. Hence, the kinematic boundary conditions of the laminate are prescribed as

$$u_z = 0 \text{ for } \sqrt{x^2 + y^2} > D_f/2 \text{ and } z = 0 \text{ and } H_L \quad (13)$$

The cylindrical impactors have identical weights and dimensions. The diameter and length of the impactors are specified as $D_p = 0.0127$ m and $H_p = 0.0142$ m, respectively. Each impactor has the same mass density specified as $\rho = 3870$ kg/m³. Their impact velocities are equal with $v_0 = 100$ m/s.

In the peridynamic model, each ply of the laminate is discretized into 179×179 material points. Also, each ply is discretized with only one grid point through the thickness at its mid-surface. The spacing between the material points in the planar and vertical directions, are, respectively, specified as $\Delta x = \Delta y = L / 179 = 0.001$ m and $\Delta z = t_k = 0.00165$ m. Thus, the boundary conditions are applied to the material points defined at the mid-surface of the bottom and top plies as

$$u_z = 0 \text{ for } \sqrt{x^2 + y^2} > D_f/2 \text{ and } z = t_k / 2 \text{ and } H_L - t_k / 2 \quad (14)$$

Fig. 5. Geometry of a composite laminate subjected to two rigid cylindrical impactors

The solution is achieved by coupling the peridynamic equations of motion for a laminate with the rigid body motion of impactors. The coupling is established by imposing contact conditions such that no material points in the target area can penetrate into the rigid impactors. This constraint condition results in interface forces that influence the motion of peridynamic material points as well as the cylindrical impactors. Furthermore, the numerical time integration is achieved by the explicit central difference method. The time step size of $\Delta t = 10^{-8}$ s was sufficient to obtain stable solution.

In order to understand the effect of simultaneous double impactors on the laminate response, the same panel is investigated when subjected to a single impactor. In this case, the impactor hits the laminate at the center point *A* with the same initial impact velocity of 100 m/s. However, its mass density is doubled so that the same amount of linear momentum is achieved between single- and double-impactor events.

Due to the single and double impactor events, the deformed configurations of the laminate are shown in Figs. 6 and 7. In the case of a single impactor, symmetric deformation occurs, while the two impactors lead to a non-symmetric deformation. As shown in Figs. 6 and 7, the cylindrical impactors punch the top face of the laminate, and create a local deformation resembling the flat end(s) of the impactor(s).

Fig. 6. Deformed configuration of laminate subjected to single cylindrical impactor: (a) top, and (b) bottom views.

Fig. 7. Deformed configuration of laminate subjected to two simultaneous cylindrical impactors: (a) top, and (b) bottom views.

As evident in Fig. 8a, the single impactor experiences higher dipping than those of the double impactors. This is consistent with the out-of-plane deflection of the laminate at point *A* as shown in Fig. 8b. The linear momentum of the single impactor is identical to that of double impactors. However, the entire kinetic energy of the single impactor is concentrated around point *A* while it is spread around a larger area in the case of double impactors.

Fig.8 Due to single- and double-impactor events: (a) Impactor displacements, and (b) Transverse deflection of the laminate.

The damage plots for all layers obtained at times $t = 4 \times 10^{-5}$ s and $t = 18.5 \times 10^{-5}$ s are shown in exploded views in Figures 9 and 10 for single- and double-impactor events, respectively. As expected, the loading due to single impactor, which hits the laminate at the center, leads to symmetric progressive damage in all of the layers. However, the damage progression due to double impactors is not symmetric. Also, the extent of the damage in the case of single impactor event appears to be higher than that of double-impactor event, mainly due to the fact that all the impact energy is concentrated at a single point rather than around two impact points. Consistent with the experimental observations, the extent and severity of the damage occurs at the bottom layer of the laminate for both loading impact events.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The ability of the PD modeling to predict the damage due to simultaneous multiple impacts is demonstrated. The PD simulations capture accurate deformation fields and complex failure morphology consistent with experimental observations. Based on the results and observations, the peridynamic theory is a viable analysis method for modeling and predicting the impact resistance of laminated composites.

Fig. 9 Layerwise damage at (a) $t = 4 \times 10^{-5}$ s and (b) $t = 18.5 \times 10^{-5}$ s due to a single impactor

Fig. 10 Layerwise damage at (a) $t = 4 \times 10^{-5}$ s and (b) $t = 18.5 \times 10^{-5}$ s due to double impactors

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